

EDUCATIONAL DIALOGUE AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

Abstract. Currently, much attention is paid to the problem of educational dialogue; psychological and pedagogical literature reveals aspects of its use as a means of developing the general culture of the individual and its individual components in the educational process. Educational dialogue is a universal means of communication and creative interaction between equal participants in the educational process. The purpose of the article is to theoretically analyze and experimentally explore the methodology of using dialogue as a way of developing students' communicative competence.

In the modern educational space, socio-psychological problems concerning the communication process, especially its communicative side, are of particular importance (B.G. Ananyev, A.A. Bodalev, I.A. Zimnyaya, A.B. Mudrik, V.N. Myasishchev) [1]. The most important qualitative characteristic that allows a developing personality to realize their needs for social acceptance, recognition, respect and determines the success of the socialization process is communicative competence. A feature of communicative competence is its ability to form successful individual activity in the changing conditions of the social environment. Therefore, its study is one of the main directions in modern education, since society requires a high level of communicative culture in humans [2].

At the stage of basic general education, the importance of developing an individual's communicative competence is also determined by the transition of students to a new age period - adolescence, in which complex processes of development of self-awareness and the formation of a value system that determines a new type of relationship with society are carried out. However, a number of psychological and pedagogical studies note the fact that in the educational process there is no system of methods and forms of work that would ensure that students achieve communicative competence (D.I. Arkharova, N.Sh. Gallyamova, T.A. Dolinina, T. A. Ladyzhenskaya, A. Yu. Maslova, O. S. Salamatova) [3]. To achieve the goals of developing communicative competence in adolescents, educational dialogue becomes an indispensable resource, understood both as a way of working on the content of a lesson and as a form of organizing learning (M.V. Clarin, V.N. Kurbanov, L.B. Tumanova) [4]. The formation of communicative competence is carried out within the framework of

dialogue between the teacher and students. Organizing dialogue in the educational process, in particular in history lessons, is a very urgent task for modern universities, since new technologies and approaches focus teachers and students on the ability to conduct dialogue, develop verbal communication, and communicate. All of the above indicates the relevance of the topic for this work, "Dialogue as a way to develop students' communicative competence."

The sensitive period for the formation of communicative competence, according to most researchers (B.G. Ananyev, L.S. Vygotsky, K.M. Gurevich, G.S. Nikiforov, E.F. Rybalko) [5], is adolescence, when communication between adolescents turns into a special type of activity that ensures the assimilation of life goals and values, moral ideals, norms and forms of behavior, increases their level of communicative competence. The development of communicative competence of adolescents in the educational process occurs through educational dialogue. Dialogue (from Greek conversation) is a form of speech consisting of a regular exchange of utterances-replicas, the linguistic composition of which is mutually influenced by the direct perception of the speech activity of the speakers [6]. Educational dialogue arose in the 4th century BC. in classical Greece and implies a special form of personally oriented development of linguistic reality, specially organized educational and cognitive activity in which knowledge is acquired, skills and abilities are formed, and a communicative culture develops. Its main purpose in teaching and upbringing is to stimulate cognitive interest, involve the class in active discussion of controversial issues, formulate moral choices and the ability to evaluate others. The educational dialogue is characterized by the following features [11]:

- the presence of a single problem of interest to all participants in the dialogue;
- the presence of two or more interlocutors connected by mutual understanding;
- possibility of free presentation of material;
- availability of feedback;
- the presence of dialogue relationships between the teacher and the class, the teacher and the student, the student and the student [6].

In university education, different types of educational dialogue are possible: teacher-class, student-class, student-student, teacher-student. The structure of the educational dialogue teacher-class can be: message of the topic; setting a learning task; joint search for a solution to a learning problem; listening to different points of view of interlocutors; adjustment; obtaining a joint final decision; generalization. Student-class (interstructural dialogue) - one student and a class are faced with a problem, a unified solution to which takes into account the opinions of their like-minded people. The purpose of such a dialogue is to find a compromise and determine the possibilities for agreement between the parties. For this type of dialogue, it is especially important to be able to understand your opponent, understand his interests, and see the problem through his eyes. This

type of dialogue is implemented in such forms as discussion and group dialogue. Student-student (intrastructural dialogue) is a form of interpersonal communication that allows, through mutual efforts, to find solutions that satisfy both parties, uniting participants for further joint activities. Characteristic features of such a dialogue: the presence of ideas among the participants, the completeness of the information used, its reliability, clear reasoning of judgments [10]. Used in the following forms of dialogue: work in pairs, group and collective dialogues, discussion.

There are several ways to organize educational dialogue: conversation, argument, dispute, discussion, but they are not equivalent. Most often, conversations are used in lessons when the topic develops in a linear direction from the known to the new. Conversation can be used at any stage of the lesson for various educational purposes: when checking homework and independent work, explaining new material, consolidating and repeating, summing up the lesson, when answering student questions [9]. The conversation is carried out in cases where there are grounds for conversation, i.e. students have information and knowledge about the material being studied. During the conversation, students reproduce the necessary knowledge and connect it with the communicated educational material. The success of the conversation depends on the skillful formulation of a series of questions and knowledge of the expected answers of students [8].

Educational discussion, among other methods, is gradually becoming part of practice. The point of this method is to exchange views on a specific issue. Through discussion, students acquire new knowledge, strengthen their own opinions, and learn to defend them. The main function of educational discussion is to stimulate cognitive interest; auxiliary functions are teaching, development, education and control and correction.

In order for an educational task set by a teacher to result in an educational dialogue, it must act as his point of view, a mature personal position that stimulates students to be creative. To ensure understanding of the material being presented, the teacher must reveal not only the meaning of an element of educational content, but also its meaning in context with other elements of social experience. Teaching, therefore, is a type of communication; the teacher and student act as communicants in the dialogical relationship "teacher - student." The professional task of the teacher is to help the student see in the general problem that unique twist that comes into contact with the student's personal problems and thoughts. It should not interfere with the process of redefining educational problems, and should not prevent students from posing new problems in the classroom [7].

Thus, educational dialogue is understood not only as a special form of learning, in which educational tasks are posed in the form of unsolved problems, but also as a form of learning and a type of relationship in the process of joint cognitive activity. Correct organization of educational dialogue by a teacher will

allow teenagers to increase their cognitive interest, involve the class in an active discussion of controversial issues, form responsible moral choices and teach them to evaluate and respect others, i.e. improves the communicative competence of students.

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